

Blind Cluster Quantum Computation- An Introduction of various Methods and Approaches with the Formal KM layer

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Abstract: This paper on the Theory of Quantum Computation provides an outline of modern day Quantum computation with its drawbacks and limitations and provides various solutions using existing or newer Models and Approaches. This paper will enlighten us to get a broader aspect of the recent day technology of computer evolution and why this QC still remains a mere concept

Keywords: Quantum Computation; KM Layer; Cluster Computing; Cloud Computing; Blind Computing

I. INTRODUCTION

A quantum computer is a device that can arbitrarily manipulate the quantum state of a part of itself. The field of quantum computation is largely a body of theoretical promises for some impressively fast algorithms which could be executed on quantum computers. The elementary unit of quantum information and the basic building block of quantum computation is the qubit, a two-level quantum system that can be prepared, manipulated and measured in a controlled way. A quantum computer can be seen as a collection of n qubits and therefore its wave function resides in a 2^{TM} -dimensional complex Hilbert space. As far as coupling to the environment may be neglected, its evolution in time is unitary and governed by the Schrodinger equation. A quantum computation is composed of three basic steps: preparation of the input state, implementation of the desired unitary transformation acting on this state and measurement of the output state. The output of the measurement process is inherently probabilistic and the probabilities of the different possible outputs are set by the basic postulates of quantum mechanics. Therefore, in a quantum algorithm we must, in general, repeat several times the algorithm to obtain the correct solution of our problem with probability as close to one as desired. In this sense, quantum algorithms are analogous to classical probabilistic algorithms. However, the superposition principle and quantum entanglement open up new possibilities for computation. Quantum computers are potentially more powerful than classical (deterministic or probabilistic) computers due to quantum interference and entanglement.

Why use quantum computation?

Advantages of QC

So, what is the big difference between classical transistors and qubits? Transistors as we know them now have two different states, 1 or 0, and can be controlled by a voltage that comes through the base of the transistor and is limited by resistors. The resistors help control the voltage and either saturate the transistor, or send voltage through it to reach the state wanted. "The difference between these transistors and the new qubits is that the qubits have 4 different states; 00, 01, 10, 11, which allows it to compute thousands of times faster than a modern day classical computer. The advantage of being able to calculate much faster will improve many aspects of life. "One of the ways that a quantum computer will be able to help the future is much like the actions of a super computer such as Watson (Stahl 2013)." Hospitals would benefit because much like supercomputers in hospitals now, they can be implemented into robotics, and also they can help search for better pharmaceutical cures by comparing billions of medical cases and going over a lot of information at once. They can also find faster routes for delivery men and all because they can run many more paths at the same time. A good example of this is the traveling business salesman. He wants to figure out the fastest route from town to town, but the only way to do this is run each possibility and then compare. This would take an entire lifetime. "Well, a quantum computer could run every one of these routes at the same time and give the best answer (Love 2013)." This is because a quantum computer basically does everything at the same time because of the superposition of the states of the qubits. Insanely enough, this simulates doing something, then going back in time, and doing it again, and then repeating that until the final answer is achieved, and in real time this is much faster than a normal computer or person could ever achieve. This theory of quantum mechanics is very confusing for those that study it, moreover for those who do not study it.

A third advantage of a quantum computer is the ability to encrypt data and security to a much more intense level. “Quantum computers will be able to produce virtually unbreakable codes, and increase data encryption and security (Love 2013).” This is a big advance, especially with people worrying about how secure the new “cloud” is. The major companies that will gain from quantum computing are the companies that are already putting time and money into research of the field.

Disadvantages of such Quantum Based Systems

Unfortunately, there is a downside to the quantum computing industry. The biggest disadvantage is the fact that it has not been totally invented yet, and people are still making parts and projections about what this computer shall resemble. “Many of the scientists that lead the field in quantum computing are still expecting decades before quantum computers appear in the home or office (Danu 2012).”

Another downside to the quantum computing is that there are many things that need to happen to make quantum computing accessible to the world. “One fact about quantum computing is that the quantum processor by D-Wave needs to be kept at .02 K (Love 2013).” For those who are not science majors, .02 K is below the temperature of the universe, and very close to absolute Kelvin, which is the lowest temperature possible. This is a very hard temperature to maintain and control.

Also, quantum processors are very unstable. “Even when they first came out it was impossible to test them without disrupting their very unstable state (Diep 2013).” Now they have figured out a new test, but in the Ted Talk, Andres Ambans, a quantum algorithm writer, also discusses how unstable the computers are. This is a problem that needs to be solved before quantum computers will appear on the shelves of a Best Buy nearest you.

The main problem with quantum computing is to actually develop it as a personal computer, and hopefully they will be in the price range of every day consumers. It will be comparable to when computers were first introduced. They were the size of a room and were very costly. Then they kept getting smaller and smaller and eventually appeared on the market. Most likely, the same sort of transition from those computers to quantum computers will take place, at first they will be accessible only to big businesses but then they will go on the commercial market. The main people that will lose out because of quantum computing are the companies who did not learn the lesson of history. This refers to the companies that did not invest in computers and stuck with punch card and tabulating technology because they did not believe that computers would become so popular, and these companies went out of business.

Economic Review of QC

Economically, quantum computers are out of reach for the modern-day customer. The first quantum processor costs about 10 million dollars and is available for purchase from D-Wave, a company out of Canada. They are called D-Wave, because they used d-wave flip flops, a type of transistor logic gate (TTL), to further their knowledge of quantum computing (Diep 2013). In order to discuss the future economics of quantum computing, it is necessary to review the past economics. This is since it is presently too soon to determine, but the history of computers will most likely give a good insight to the future of quantum computing.

In 1949, one of the first computers ever built was the Electronic Delay Storage Automatic Calculator (EDSAC). “This computer ran on vacuum tubes, and covered the area of 215 square feet (Horn yak 2011).” This is a very big area, and it was very doubtful that a computer that size could ever be reduced to something the size of a laptop. The U.K. is interested in rebuilding the computer, and in modern day money, they predict it will cost about \$350,000 (Horn yak 2011). The price of computers did decrease however; “In 1980, IBM did develop the first personal computer and coined the term PC. This machine would have cost about \$4,000 in today’s money (Bellis 2013).” The world saw the price and size of the computer dramatically reduced, and the improbability of never owning a computer or seeing one in a home was diminished.

The next innovation in computing was the Supercomputer. “IBM built the Roadrunner, which cost \$100 Million to build (IBM 2013).” This computer is now shut down, and many more have been developed and at a cheaper cost. A supercomputer is a lot faster than a regular computer, but comes at a steep price not only in the setup, but also the maintenance. The computers have to be cooled to a very low temperature, and also require a very large power source. “Companies have been working on ‘green’ supercomputers that are more environmental friendly (Dongarra et al., 2013).” They are now working on reducing the costs and providing cheaper versions. “Now a ‘personal’ supercomputer can be available for \$500,000, which is the smaller cousin to the other supercomputer offered by Cray which costs around \$10-13 Million (Goring 2013).” This is also a dramatic price decrease for the supercomputers size and an increase in availability.

Looking at the history of computers, we could predict that a quantum computer could be available on the consumer markets, but not at least for another decade or so (Marian 2013). The history shows that computers are usually way too big and way too expensive, and then technology improves and gets smaller and cheaper just as Moore’s Law predicts

Ethics in Quantum System

The invention of supercomputers also produced new challenges for ethical decision making. These supercomputers have insanely fast computing processors compared to a personal computer. What can these supercomputers do? They can break down codes, and passwords, and could be used for hacking. This is a big problem when we put all of our banking information online, and other valuable or private information. Considering what these supercomputers can do, it is vital to also think about how a quantum computer is capable of performing. A quantum computer is thousands of times faster than a standard computer, and will use four state qubits instead of the traditional two state transistors. This allows for exponentially greater computing ability, and allows for someone that is very familiar with the quantum computer to have a significant advantage over the rest of the computer population.

Hackers today use bot-nets to hack into many computers and string them together, which has already been done using regular computers. This crime is so commonplace place that in 2008 “the government [had] estimated that 10-15% of computers had been taken over by hackers and they had a network of computers which has more computing power than the government” (Leamy 2008). When quantum computers are developed, the world will have a potential security crisis to deal with. It will be difficult to determine if the computers should be released to the consumer market or only used for governments and corporate businesses. This also creates an ethical dilemma because according to the ACM Code of Ethics, “People need to have equal access to computers” (2013). The choice not to allow personal quantum computers would result in a substantial inequality for access to computers.

Currently, we can compare the availability of supercomputers and predict how quantum computers will be accessible when they are developed. Right now supercomputers can be considered ethically wrong since this code stipulates that every country needs to have the same access to them. "Out of the top 500 supercomputers in the world the United States, Germany, China, and United Kingdom have a lot more, and more powerful supercomputers, thus having a great advantage over everyone else, and creating an unequal opportunity (Danara et al., 2013)." Presently, quantum computers are not available because they are still being developed, and there is no telling how soon they will be available due to the problem of the fragile state of the processor. However, a similar situation has happened in the past. When the first computers were introduced, no one believed it would be possible to develop a personal computer, which obviously proved false. It stands to reason that quantum computers may follow a similar path.

Another ethical problem surrounding quantum computers is the Intellectual Property clause in the Stanford Ethical Guide, which states that people want to control rights to software ownership (Bynum 2008). This creates a problem because people want to own and patent certain mathematical equations and software. This is a controversial debate because math equations are not really property and should be available to everyone. This applies to quantum computing because they are presently developing a quantum algorithm and when they do, if they put a patent on it, it would basically monopolize the entire quantum computing field. "Tom Wong, a graduate student in physics and David Meyer, professor of mathematics at the University of California, San Diego, have proposed a new algorithm for quantum computing that will speed a particular type of problem, the algorithm is patent pending right now (Brown 2013)." If he does receive a patent, then no one would be able to use the software without purchasing it first. This is a significant matter because no one can use the math that he used in his program, and it would restrict other people from improving upon his algorithm and inventing new software. As of now, it is only in the beginning phase, but in the future we will see complex and lengthy ethical debates over the topic of quantum computers.

Future Development of QC

Quantum computing is the future of computing. There is no doubt in that. From the past trends in the development of computers, it is seen that the possibilities are vast and almost even unimaginable. Right now the only thing that will hold quantum computing back is the question; is it marketable for the everyday consumer? Even though it is an exponentially faster than a normal computer, the average person does not do calculations that are over one second to calculate using a normal computer. Since no human can tell the difference between a calculation that takes a second and a calculation that is nanoseconds faster, there is almost no real reason to invest in a quantum PC for an everyday user. However, IBM predicts that quantum computing may be accessible to consumers within the next decade. Most likely, these quantum computers will be used for corporate businesses and in governments.

The creators are working on developing more stable processors and more algorithms, and when they do discover them, the possibilities of what a quantum computer can do are unfathomable. They can use the theories of quantum mechanics to operate the system, which allows for calculations that are thousands of times faster. D-Wave has developed the first processor, which have been purchased by a few companies, including NASA, for further research. The companies that are not investing in the development of quantum computation will most likely mirror the companies that did not invest in computers when they were first developed. They may end up falling behind or even being absorbed by other companies since they may be too far behind to catch up in the technology boom.

Generally, quantum computers are considered to be a note-worthy and groundbreaking invention. But as always with a great invention comes potentially even greater flaws, and it could eventually contribute to unfortunate outcomes if used with the wrong intentions. This possibility, however, is present for any significant invention. For this reason, laws and regulations must be formed so that the world can be trusted to use the technology ethically.

The most interesting conclusion that can be drawn by comparing the history of computers is that IBM was one of the leading companies that decided to invest in computers from the very beginning of the computer age, they are one of the leading supercomputer inventors, and now they are one of the leading researchers in quantum computing. By default, this leads to the conclusion that quantum computing has a very good possibility to be the future of computing, considering that IBM is one of the oldest and most intuitive computer companies.

II. SOLUTIONS USING BLIND-KM MODELS AND APPROACHES

After the detailed study of the advantages and disadvantages of quantum computation we come to a point where we need to find the solutions to the numerous drawbacks of the computational model. In this subtopic we will discuss about the various methods and models which can be implemented in the current quantum model to overcome the limitations which are still prevailing among us.

The High Performance Quantum Theory of Computers

Here we introduce the basic framework for a potential HPQC based on topological cluster state computing in the photonic regime [Fig. 1]. We discuss two possible mainframe models; one where multi-user computation is performed locally by the mainframe and another where partitions of the mainframe lattice are sent via quantum communications channels to individual users. We complete the discussion by providing an example of a partition structure for the mainframe lattice which satisfies many of the necessary components of a HPQC mainframe and give a basic estimate of the number of photonic chips required for a massive mainframe quantum server. The first model we consider we denote the trusted mainframe model. This is where individual users connect via classically secure data pathways and the mainframe host is trustworthy. Each client logs onto the host and transmits a classical data stream, corresponding to the desired quantum algorithm, to the host (via a sequence of photon measurement bases).

The mainframe will then run the quantum algorithm locally and once the computation is complete, transmits the resulting classical information back to the user. This model has very substantial benefits. First, each user does not require quantum communications channels or any quantum infrastructure locally. All that is required is that each user compile a quantum algorithm into an appropriate classical data stream which is sent to the mainframe. Additionally, the host does not need to transmit any data to the user during computation. All internal corrections to the lattice which arise due to its preparation and error correction procedures are performed within the mainframe. The only data which is transmitted to the user is the classical result from the quantum algorithm. Finally, as each user independently logs on to the system to run a quantum algorithm, the mainframe can be configured to assign resources dynamically. If one user requires a large number of logical qubits and if the mainframe load is low, then the host can adjust to allocate a larger partition of the overall lattice to one individual user.

Cluster-state quantum computation

The cluster-state model of quantum computation [5] is a beautiful alternate model of quantum computation, mathematically equivalent to the standard quantum circuit model, but quite different in physical aspect. We describe briefly the procedure used to simulate a quantum circuit in the cluster-state model; proofs may be found in [5]. Note that this is an abstract model for quantum computation, not a proposal for physical implementation, so we describe it without reference to the details of a specific physical system. To simulate a quantum circuit like that in Fig. 1 we first prepare the cluster state, an entangled network of qubits defined as in Fig. 2. Each qubit in the quantum circuit is replaced by a horizontal line of qubits in the cluster state. Different horizontal qubits represent the original qubit at different times, with the progress of time being from left to right. Each single-qubit gate in the quantum circuit is replaced by two horizontally adjacent qubits in the cluster state. (Alternately, one or three horizontally adjacent qubits could be used; that would correspond to slightly different classes of single qubit unitaries being simulated.) Cphase gates in the original circuit are simulated using a vertical "bridge" connecting the appropriate qubits. With the cluster state prepared, simulation of the circuit is accomplished using single-qubit measurements, and feedforward of measurement results to control the basis in which later measurements are performed. The sequence of measurements is illustrated in Fig. 3. The output of the circuit in Fig. 1 is the same as the state of the qubits at the end of the horizontal lines in Fig. 3, up to a known product of Pauli matrices, which can be compensated for by classical post-processing. Extending this example along similar lines, we can simulate an arbitrary quantum circuit using just cluster-state preparation, single-qubit unitaries, measurements in the computational basis, and measurement feed forward.

The Kill Layer Model Approach of Q.C

KLM encodes a single qubit in two optical modes, A and B, with logical qubit states $|0\rangle_L \equiv |01\rangle_{AB}$, and $|1\rangle_L \equiv |10\rangle_{AB}$.

State preparation is done using single-photon sources while measurements in the computational basis may be achieved using high-efficiency photodetectors. Such sources and detectors make heavy demands not entirely met by existing optical technology, although encouraging progress on both fronts has been reported recently. Arbitrary single-qubit operations are achieved using phase shifters and beam splitters.

III. CONCLUSION

We have examined several problems associated with the implementation of quantum computers and we conclude that we currently do not possess technical solutions related to the fundamental tasks of quantum gate design, state preparation, and error correction.

The basic problem of implementation is a result of quantum computation being essentially an analog process. Using unitary transformations to solve real problems involving rotations, as in factorization, is an attractive mathematical idea, but there remain fundamental engineering hurdles in the implementation of this idea

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Bibliography

Sayantana Gupta is born in Kolkata, India and has pursued Engineering in UEM Kolkata. He has keen interest in Quantum Computing and Green Computing and various other fields. Getting the right opportunity with his innovative mind his contributions will always remain useful.

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